

Real-Time Facial Recognition with Age and Gender Identification Using OpenCV

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Abstract-Face recognition is extremely crucial in today's world. Several scientists have been investigating it for several years, with an emphasis on posture lighting and expression plastic surgery. Face recognition is extremely crucial for security reasons. Face recognition is utilized for security purposes since everyone wants their stuff to be safe. As it is extremely easy to recognize the face photos of well-known individuals such as actors, athletes, politicians, social workers, and others in many sectors, as the label suggests, recognizing face images with age and weight component. A convolutional neural network and residual network structures are used to determine the age and gender of a face.

Keywords:- Face Recognition, Age Estimation And Gender Estimation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Age, gender, and emotions are just a few of the details that may be seen on a face. Age and gender are important personal identity traits that are important in social life. Artificial intelligence may be used to forecast age and gender in a number of industries, including e-commerce, security, cosmetics, and intelligent human-machine interface development. Recognizing emotions can also assist us in determining the participants' psychological condition. Estimates of age, gender, and accuracy might help to round out the input.

Using convolutional neural networks and residual network architectures, we offer a method for estimating the age, gender, and accuracy of a face. This technology may be used in the retail industry to enable businesses develop their own databases to assess the buying preferences and experiences of users of various ages and genders, and then make timely adjustments to purchase lists or operational models.

We create a face recognition system using convolutional neural network (CNN) models that can recognize faces and determine the age and gender of people in real time..

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

- A single snapshot may reveal a lot about perceived age. [10] We'll use well-known classifiers that have already been trained and made available by OpenCV in order to identify and follow a moving face. [11]
- Numerous research [3, 4, 6] and big datasets [3, 7, 9] have been published on the (biological, actual) age estimate using a single facial picture. The assessment of apparent age, or the age as seen by other people, on the other hand, is still in its early stages. The organisers of ChaLearn Looking At People 2015 [5] presented the vision community with a challenge and one of the largest datasets of images with apparent age annotations available to date.

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- VGG-16 architecture and ImageNet pretraining are used by convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for image categorization [1,8].

3. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this paper is to find Real-Time Face Recognition program to identify the Age and Gender using the given dataset with accuracy. The model should be able to classify correctly as Gender, Age and Accuracy. The dataset is divided into two training and testing data sets. The model should be trained with more data to get accuracy in learning.

The main function does the following:

- The picture is first read using the `cv2.imread()` method.
- We utilise `get_faces()` function to get all the identified faces from the image once it has been scaled to the suitable size..
- To acquire the predictions, we iterate over each identified face picture and execute `get_age_predictions()` and `get_gender_predictions()`.
- We print the age and gender, then draw a rectangle around the face and add a label with the same information to assure correctness.
- Finally, the picture is shown.

The files that must be included in the project directory are listed below.

- `gender_net.caffemodel`: The pre-trained model uses weights to identify gender.

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- `deploy_gender.prototxt`: The model architecture for the gender detection model, which is a simple text file with a JSON-like structure that contains all of the specifications for the neural network layer.
- `age_net.caffemodel`: For age detection, the pre-trained model uses weights.
- `deploy_age.prototxt`: Design of the age detection model (a simple text file with a JSON-like syntax that contains all of the definitions for the neural network layer).
- `res10_300x300_ssd_iter_140000_fp16.caffe` model: The pre-trained model includes weights for detecting faces.
- `deploy.prototxt.txt`: This is the face detection model's model architecture.

4. BUILD MODEL

The model building is the main step in the face detection. While building the model user use the algorithms. The steps involved are:

Loading the models:-

```
23 # Initialize frame size
24 frame_width = 1280
25 frame_height = 720
26 # load face Caffe model
27 face_net = cv2.dnn.readNetFromCaffe(FACE_PROTO, FACE_MODEL)
28 # Load age prediction model
29 age_net = cv2.dnn.readNetFromCaffe(AGE_MODEL, AGE_PROTO)
30 # Load gender prediction model
31 gender_net = cv2.dnn.readNetFromCaffe(GENDER_MODEL, GENDER_PROTO)
```

We need a function to detect faces before we can try to detect age and gender:-

```

33 def get_faces(frame, confidence_threshold=0.5):
34     # convert the frame into a blob to be ready for NN input
35     blob = cv2.dnn.blobFromImage(frame, 1.0, (300, 300), (104, 177.0, 123.0))
36     # set the image as input to the NN
37     face_net.setInput(blob)
38     # perform inference and get predictions
39     output = np.squeeze(face_net.forward())
40     # initialize the result list
41     faces = []
42     # Loop over the faces detected
43     for i in range(output.shape[0]):
44         confidence = output[i, 2]
45         if confidence > confidence_threshold:
46             box = output[i, 3:7] * \
47                 np.array([frame.shape[1], frame.shape[0],
48                         frame.shape[1], frame.shape[0]])
49             # convert to integers
50             start_x, start_y, end_x, end_y = box.astype(np.int)
51             # widen the box a little
52             start_x, start_y, end_x, end_y = start_x - \
53                 10, start_y - 10, end_x + 10, end_y + 10
54             start_x = 0 if start_x < 0 else start_x
55             start_y = 0 if start_y < 0 else start_y
56             end_x = 0 if end_x < 0 else end_x
57             end_y = 0 if end_y < 0 else end_y
58             # append to our list
59             faces.append((start_x, start_y, end_x, end_y))
60     return faces

```

Let's define our age and gender detection functions now that everything is in place:

```

88 def get_gender_predictions(face_img):
89     blob = cv2.dnn.blobFromImage(
90         image=face_img, scalefactor=1.0, size=(227, 227),
91         mean=MODEL_MEAN_VALUES, swapRB=False, crop=False
92     )
93     gender_net.setInput(blob)
94     return gender_net.forward()
95
96
97 def get_age_predictions(face_img):
98     blob = cv2.dnn.blobFromImage(
99         image=face_img, scalefactor=1.0, size=(227, 227),
100        mean=MODEL_MEAN_VALUES, swapRB=False
101    )
102    age_net.setInput(blob)
103    return age_net.forward()

```

When the supplied images are wider than a predetermined width, we'll need it to resize them:

```

63 def image_resize(image, width = None, height = None, inter = cv2.INTER_AREA):
64     # initialize the dimensions of the image to be resized and
65     # grab the image size
66     dim = None
67     (h, w) = image.shape[:2]
68     # if both the width and height are None, then return the
69     # original image
70     if width is None and height is None:
71         return image
72     # check to see if the width is None
73     if width is None:
74         # calculate the ratio of the height and construct the
75         # dimensions
76         r = height / float(h)
77         dim = (int(w * r), height)
78     # otherwise, the height is None
79     else:
80         # calculate the ratio of the width and construct the
81         # dimensions
82         r = width / float(w)
83         dim = (width, int(h * r))
84     # resize the image
85     return cv2.resize(image, dim, interpolation = inter)

```

Last but not least, we write our main function:-

```

107 def predict_age_and_gender():
108     """Predict the gender of the faces showing in the image"""
109     # create a new cam object
110     cap = cv2.VideoCapture(0)
111
112     while True:
113         _, img = cap.read()
114         # Take a copy of the initial image and resize it
115         frame = img.copy()
116         # resize if higher than frame_width
117         if frame.shape[1] > frame_width:
118             frame = image_resize(frame, width=frame_width)
119         # predict the faces
120         faces = get_faces(frame)
121         # Loop over the faces detected
122         # for idx, face in enumerate(faces):

```

```

123         for i, (start_x, start_y, end_x, end_y) in enumerate(faces):
124             face_img = frame[start_y: end_y, start_x: end_x]
125             # predict age
126             age_preds = get_age_predictions(face_img)
127             # predict gender
128             gender_preds = get_gender_predictions(face_img)
129             i = gender_preds[0].argmax()
130             gender = GENDER_LIST[i]
131             gender_confidence_score = gender_preds[0][i]
132             i = age_preds[0].argmax()
133             age = AGE_INTERVALS[i]
134             age_confidence_score = age_preds[0][i]
135             # Draw the box
136             label = "(gender: {gender_confidence_score*100:.1f}%, (age: {age_confidence_score*100:.1f}%"
137             # label = "(gender: {gender_confidence_score*100:.1f}%, (age: {age_confidence_score*100:.1f}%"
138             print(label)
139             yPos = start_y - 15

```

```

140             while yPos < 15:
141                 yPos += 15
142                 box_color = (255, 0, 0) if gender == "Male" else (147, 20, 255)
143                 cv2.rectangle(frame, (start_x, start_y), (end_x, end_y), box_color, 2)
144                 # Label processed image
145                 cv2.putText(frame, label, (start_x, yPos),
146                             cv2.FONT_HERSHEY_SIMPLEX, 0.54, box_color, 2)
147
148             # Display processed image
149             cv2.imshow("Gender Estimator", frame)
150             if cv2.waitKey(1) == ord('q'):
151                 break
152             # Uncomment if you want to save the image
153             # cv2.imwrite("output.jpg", frame)
154
155     # Cleanup
156     cv2.destroyAllWindows()

```

Let's call it:-

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```
158 | if __name__ == "__main__":  
159 |     predict_age_and_gender()
```

5. RESULT

We utilized a camera to determine the age and gender of a person's face in real time. And the estimations' outcomes are displayed below. The anticipated gender, age, and accuracy are presented above the faces, correspondingly. In the case of age prediction, it is thought that an inaccuracy of plus or minus two years is acceptable. We conducted various tests and discovered that the forecast accuracy rate for gender and age is the greatest, at more than 80%.

6. CONCLUSION

Age and gender recognition, on the other hand, is a far more challenging challenge than many other PC vision tasks. The expertise required to build these kinds of frameworks is the primary cause of this difficulty gap. Unlike standard article searching missions, which may require tens of thousands or even hundreds of thousands of photos for preparation, datasets including age and gender names are often in the thousands, if not hundreds of thousands. Python gathered photographs, and the model performed poorly in terms of accuracy; the model approach has to be refined further.

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